

*Effect of Ampicillin Sodium Treatment on the Pattern of Nephrotoxicity in Wild Tropical Rodent, Indian Palm Squirrel, *F. pennanti*.*

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Introduction:

Ampicillin is very often used by clinicians in treating infections, out of which Tetracycline's are well known for producing Nephrotoxic effects (side effects). Nephrotoxicity caused by Ampicillin has recently been noted (Deb et al., 1986). At higher doses Ampicillin has been reported to be nephrotoxic in case reports. It has also been reported that Ampicillin at higher doses increases the level of creatinine and urea in serum and urine. In fact the toxic effects of widely used antibiotic drugs are due to the result of oxidative reaction that takes place during its metabolism. Notable among the ameliorating agents for above are antioxidants, which include different classes of compounds that include beta blockers, superoxide dismutase mimetic agents, hormones, iron chelators, vitamins and medicinal plants.

Oxidative stress and antioxidant defense One of the factors that plays a major role in many pathological situations including cancer, ischemia/reperfusion injury, neurodegenerative disorders and even aging, is the excessive generation of free radicals (Harman, 1981; Kehrer, 1993; Knight, 1998). Free radicals are molecules which contain an unpaired number of electrons in their valence orbital; this makes them highly unstable and extraordinarily reactive. Among these agents are reactive oxygen species (ROS) which react and damage essential molecules within the cells including lipids, proteins and DNA (de Groot, 1994; Toyokuni, 1999). In conditions where there is excessive ROS, the resulting molecular destruction is identified as oxidative damage (Pierrefiche and Laborit, 1995). Reactive oxygen species are formed naturally during many metabolic processes and, thus, cells have developed diverse mechanisms to reduce the deleterious consequences of ROS. To protect themselves against ROS, cells have developed an antioxidant defense which includes enzymatic and non enzymatic mechanisms. ROS and the antioxidant defense must be in perfect equilibrium to avoid that the relation between ROS formation and depuration being unbalanced. Enzymes involved in the elimination of ROS include superoxide dismutases (SOD). Besides the enzymatic antioxidant system, there are non enzymatic antioxidants, or free radical scavengers, which remove ROS directly because of their electron donating ability thereby neutralizing potential ROS toxicity. The best known non enzymatic antioxidants are vitamin E (α -tocopherol), vitamin C (ascorbate), glutathione (GSH) and b-carotene.

In rodents it is first experiment to find the nephrotoxicity of Ampicillin in a wild tropical rodent *Funambulus pennanti*. In previous studies with rats we have found that Ampicillin produces nephrotoxicity at a dose even lower than the dose used for clinical trials and drug delivery systems. The animal model we have used in our previous studies was *Rattus norvegicus* a laboratory animal which faces minimal or least challenges from the environmental conditions and xenobiotic substances. This wild rodent Indian palm squirrel have been used in our lab for last two decades and is easily available in and around Varanasi, it faces similar environmental challenges as is faced by human population.

Materials and Methods:

Thirty five (35) male squirrels (weighing 100g to 120g each) were used in this study. The squirrels were collected from the field and acclimatized for a week in a room fully exposed to ambient environmental conditions (Light 12.50 hr; Temp. 20–25°C; Humidity, 29–50%). The animals were housed in wire net cages (25" X 75" X 30") and had an access to food consisting of soaked gram seeds (*Cicer arietinum*), nuts and water ad libitum. Later, the squirrels were divided into five groups of 7 animals in each cage.

Group I: Control

Seven male squirrels were kept in natural environmental condition as mentioned above without any treatment (NDL).

Group II: Vehicle (Triple Distilled Water) treated

Seven male squirrels were kept in natural environmental condition as mentioned above. A single intra venous dose of TDW was given (1ml/kg body wt.) every day.

Group III: Ampicillin treated

Seven male squirrels were kept in natural environmental condition as mentioned above. A single dose of Ampicillin sodium (40mg/Kg body wt.) reconstituted in TDS was given every day between 10am to 11am.

Sample collection:

All the treatments were given for seven days and on the eighth day that is after 24 hours of last treatments animals were decapitated. The bladder was surgically extruded and emptied by supra-pubic puncture. This procedure ensured collection of urine produced over a period of 60 min. At the time of sacrifice, thus urine was collected, and its volume was measured and biochemical parameters ACP, ALP, Creatinine and Urea were estimated. After removal of both kidneys through a midline abdominal incision, the right and left kidneys were processed. The kidneys were stripped from their capsule, weighed, and slit by longitudinal incision. Cortical, medullary (outer medulla), and papillary (inner medulla-papillary tip) components were separated under a dissecting microscope. The accuracy of the dissection was verified by light microscopy. Kidney tissues were also fixed in Bouin's fluid for histology.

Renal cortical tissue homogenates were prepared separately (as mentioned in materials and methods) for the detection of Superoxide dismutase activity (SOD), lipid peroxidation level (TBARS) and Total antioxidative status (TAS %). Trunk Blood was collected in separate centrifuge tubes for biochemical estimations that are BUN, ACP, ALP, Creatinine and Total kidney cortical protein.

Histology:

After fixation in Bouin's fluid for 22 hours, kidney was paraffin embedded and cut into 6- μ m sections. Deparaffinized sections were stained using hematoxylin and eosin. Kidney morphology was observed under microscope (Leica MPV-3, Germany). The morphometric analysis of capsular space and cellular integrity (PCT, DCT & glomerulus) of kidney cortical region were done in 20 serial sections randomly selected from each animal with the help of filar ocular micrometer (Webcon Pvt. Ltd. India)

Statistical analysis:

All the data were expressed as means \pm SEM of at least five animals per group. Data comparisons were statistically analyzed by using ANOVA followed by Student Newman-Keuls' multiple range tests. The differences were considered statistically significant when $p < 0.05$ (Bruning and Knitz, 1977). Microsoft Excel program was used for statistical calculations.

Results:

Biochemical estimation of ACP, ALP, Creatinine and Urea in blood and urine showed significant ($p < 0.01$) increase in groups treated with Ampicillin sodium compared to controls, TDW and vehicle treated ones. There was slight decrease of blood ACP and Urea in groups treated with saline which was not significant (Fig. 1&2). Increase in TBARS level of ampicillin treated groups were highly significant while Total antioxidative capacity (TAS %) and Total blood proteins decreased significantly ($p < 0.01$) when compared to all other groups. Increase in Superoxide dismutase activity (SOD) in vehicle treated groups was non significant but decrease in SOD activity in ampicillin treated groups was significant (Fig. 3). Histological observation showed significant ($p < 0.01$) decrease in capsular space in Ampicillin treated groups while there was no significant change observed in the groups treated with TDW and control (Plate1).

Fig. 1

Effect of Ampicillin on acid phosphatase (ACP) in (A) blood, (B) urine and alkaline phosphatase (ALP) in (C) blood, (D) urine of *F. pennanti*. Histogram represent Mean + SEM (N=7), Vertical bar on each histogram represent standard error of mean. Significance of difference ** $p < 0.01$; Control (Con) vs Vehicle (Veh) and Ampicillin treated (Amp) groups.

Fig. 2

Effect of Ampicillin on (A) blood urea nitrogen (BUN), (B) urine urea and creatinine in (C) blood, (D) urine of *F. pennanti*. Histogram represent Mean + SEM (N=7), Vertical bar on each histogram represent standard error of mean. Significance of difference ** $p < 0.01$; Control (Con) vs Vehicle (Veh) and Ampicillin treated (Amp) groups.

Fig. 3

(A) Effect of Ampicillin on the malon-dialdehyde level (TBARS) of *F. pennanti*. Histogram represent Mean + SEM (N=7), Vertical bar on each histogram represent standard error of mean. Significance of difference ** $p < 0.01$; Control (Con) vs Vehicle (Veh) and Ampicillin treated (Amp) groups.

(B) Effect of Ampicillin on the total kidney cortical protein weight of *F. pennanti*. Histogram represent Mean + SEM (N=7), Vertical bar on each histogram represent standard error of mean. Significance of difference ** $p < 0.01$; Control (Con) vs Vehicle (Veh) and Ampicillin treated (Amp) groups.

(C) Effect of Ampicillin on super oxide-dismutase activity (SOD) of *F. pennanti*. Histogram represent Mean + SEM (N=7), Vertical bar on each histogram represent standard error of mean. Significance of difference ** $p < 0.01$; Control (Con) vs Vehicle (Veh) and Ampicillin treated (Amp) groups.

(D) Effect of Ampicillin on the total antioxidative status (TAS %) of *F. pennanti*. Histogram represent Mean + SEM (N=7), Vertical bar on each histogram represent standard error of mean. Significance of difference ** $p < 0.01$; Control (Con) vs Vehicle (Veh) and Ampicillin treated (Amp) groups.

Plate 1

Histomicrograph of squirrel kidney cortical region showing glomerulus (G), capsular space (→), Brush bordered vesicular epithelial cells (BBVEC) (*) of proximal convoluted tubule (PCT), distal convoluted tubule (DCT), loop of henele and collecting tubule. (Under 40X objective)

- A- Control (Con)
- B- Vehicle treated (Veh)
- C- Ampicillin treated (Amp)

Discussion:

Increase in alkaline phosphatase, acid phosphatase, creatinine and urea in urine as well as in blood following Ampicillin treatment indicates the direct toxic effects of Ampicillin on the above parameters when compared to controls. Lipid per oxidation level was found significantly high in Ampicillin treated groups, when compared to controls. The reason of such effects could be due to the oxidative stress i. e. free radical load induced by Ampicillin metabolism. Cytosolic protein levels of kidney cortical region were significantly high in Ampicillin treated groups when compared with the controls. The new proteins would have been synthesized to adapt the degradation caused by Ampicillin and the proteins from membrane might have mobilized in the cytosol due to lipid peroxidation. The total antioxidative status decreased following the Ampicillin treatment may be due to high free radical generation by Ampicillin toxicity (metabolism). To combat this free radical load, antioxidative enzymes would have increased their activity more or some extra antioxidative enzyme might have been produced following melatonin treatment.

Ampicillin treatment reduced the SOD activity below the control levels indicating presence/involvement of less super oxide radicals, which also indicates that the ampicillin toxicity is not mediated or caused by SOD radicals. It could be that Hydroxyl radicals (OH) are being affected by Ampicillin and it will be the next target of the study. Result clearly indicates that Ampicillin is causing nephrotoxicity by inducing free radical load probably other than superoxide (SOD) radicals. Ampicillin to some extent but not completely as proved in our previous experiments. Since the results are of high clinical value further dose dependent studies were accomplished. There are some experimental data suggesting that nephrotoxic drugs may also change levels of MDA, GSH, BUN and Cr (Ozbek et al., 2000; Parlakpinar, 2004) which are commonly used to monitor the development and extent of renal tubular damage due to oxidative stress. It has also been reported that the light and electron microscopic assessments were more sensitive than the other methods in determining toxicity (Klein et al., 1992). Aminoglycosides are not metabolized in the body, and most of the injected dose is excreted through urine, whereas a fraction accumulates in the renal proximal tubule cells, where the concentration of aminoglycosides is several times higher than in the plasma. The concentrated accumulation of Ampicillin in the proximal tubule cells would be associated with nephrotoxicity as observed in histological by our group and others (Humes, 1988). In addition to scavenging free radicals such as the hydroxyl radical, singlet oxygen, peroxy radical and the peroxy nitrite anion, melatonin also reduces their generation (Humes, 1988; Tan et al., 2002; Acuna-Castroviejo et al., 2001).

Probably the property of melatonin to rapidly enter cells would be an important feature in reducing ampicillin-induced toxicity, melatonin reduced lipid peroxidation, serum BUN and Cr, and elevated GSH levels induced by renal ischemia reperfusion (Antolin, 1996) and nephrotoxic agents including cisplatin (Reiter et al., 1998, 2000; Tomas-Zapico et al., 2002), doxorubicin and daunorubicin (Tomas-Zapico et al., 2002; Mayo et al., 2002) reported that pre- and post-treatment with a low pharmacologic dose of melatonin attenuated lipid peroxidation levels caused by adriamycin. Taking into consideration the free radicals produced by various immune cells as a part of Ampicillin action mechanism for microbial killing, the two antioxidant treatment has been taken for our next study.

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